

Identification of heat stress-related genomic regions by genome-wide association study in *Solanum tuberosum*

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ABSTRACT

The climate crisis impairs yield and quality of crucial crops like potatoes. We investigated the effects of heat stress on five morpho-physiological parameters in a diverse panel of 178 potato cultivars under glasshouse conditions. Overall, heat stress increased shoot elongation and green fresh weight, but reduced tuber yield, starch content and harvest index. Genomic information was obtained from 258 tetraploid and three diploid cultivars by a genotyping-by-sequencing approach using methylation-sensitive restriction enzymes. This resulted in an enrichment of sequences in gene-rich regions. Population structure analyses using genetic distances and hierarchical clustering revealed strong kinship but weak overall population structure cultivars. A genome-wide association study (GWAS) was conducted with a subset of 20 K stringently filtered SNPs to identify quantitative trait loci (QTL) linked to heat tolerance. We identified 67 QTL and established haploblock boundaries to narrow down the number of candidate genes. Additionally, GO-enrichment analyses provided insights into gene functions. Heritability and genomic prediction were conducted to assess the usability of the collected data for selecting breeding material. The detected QTL might be exploited in marker-assisted selection to develop heat-resilient potato cultivars.

1. Introduction

Global climate change is expected to lead to a rise in global surface temperature of up to 5.7 °C by the end of the 21st century. Elevated temperature already results in an increase of extreme and unpredictable local weather events like drought and heat periods [1]. Many crop species struggle to maintain high yield and quality under such extreme weather conditions. Abiotic stresses like drought, heat, cold, or salinity can diminish crop yield by 50 to 70 % [2]. Furthermore, a predicted increase in human population of up to 9 billion people by 2050 [3] and a reduction of prime farmland due to desertification and urbanization require a stable and efficient agriculture even under suboptimal conditions. These challenges demand a drastic increase in major food crop production over the next 50 years [4]. Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.) is essential for global food security. It is the most important non-grain crop consumed worldwide [5]. The well-balanced composition of its tubers

made of starch, proteins, minerals, and vitamins makes it a crucial staple food, feed and a valuable resource for many industrial applications. Potato plants originate from the Andes and favour the tempered growing conditions that are characteristic of that region. They are particularly susceptible to elevated temperatures [6]. It is predicted that potato tuber yields will decline by 18–32 % due to climate change by the middle of this century [7]. The susceptibility of potato to heat stress varies among different cultivars and is influenced by factors like the growth stage, maturity group, duration and severity of the stress [8–13]. A survey conducted among European farmers revealed a high demand for yield-stable, climate change adapted varieties, which emphasises the need for research towards heat-resistant plants [14].

Heat causes molecular, biochemical, physiological, and morphological changes in plants to adapt or acclimate to these changes. For instance, hyponasty and increased internode elongation, generally known as thermomorphogenesis, are induced to improve the air

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circulation of the plant [15–17], while increased transpiration helps to cool the leaf surface. One major consequence of heat on the biochemical level is an increased production of reactive oxygen species (ROS), which can trigger lipid peroxidation of cell membranes, protein denaturation and DNA damage [18–21]. However, ROS also function as signaling molecules to induce downstream signaling cascades to adjust the plant's metabolism to the prevailing conditions [18,20]. Among the pivotal biochemical responses are the synthesis of ROS-scavenging low molecular antioxidants and enzymes, compatible solutes and heat shock proteins (HSPs) to maintain the cellular homeostasis [18].

In potato, already moderately elevated temperatures can delay tuber formation and bulking by disturbing the source-sink balance [6,8,22]. A reduced assimilate production caused by a decreased photosynthetic productivity contributes to a lower amount of assimilates (sucrose) that are produced and transported from photosynthetically active source leaves via the phloem to sink tissues such as developing tubers [23,24]. Lower sucrose availability affects activity of starch biosynthesis enzymes in growing tubers, contributing to reduced tuber starch contents and lower tuber yield [8,18,25–27]. The development of heat-resilient potato cultivars requires a detailed understanding of molecular processes as well as the identification of molecular markers which can be integrated into novel breeding strategies [26,28,29].

Nowadays, genome-wide association studies (GWAS) are regularly conducted to detect associations between genetic variants and traits and have successfully been applied for the discovery of several loci associated with important agronomic traits in various species, including potato [30–37]. However, potato is autotetraploid and highly heterozygous with high genomic complexity, which renders prediction of performance during breeding difficult [38]. Moreover, cultivated potato shows strong family-based relationship but weak overall population structure, thereby aggravating formation of genomic clusters when conducting population structure analysis [39–41], which is necessary for statistical breeding methods such as GWAS or genomic prediction. Nonetheless, extensive progress has been made within recent years towards the discovery of quantitative trait loci (QTL) associated with either tuber quality traits or biotic stresses like late blight or common scab in *S. tuberosum* [30–32,36]. Less research has been directed towards the identification of QTL concerning the adaptation to abiotic stresses in potato such as drought and heat [33–35,42,43]. Heat adaptation is a complex trait and understanding its genetic basis is crucial for breeding purposes [43–45]. Using a nodal cutting tuberization assay, Trapero-Mozos et al. identified HSc70 as a candidate gene associated with maintaining tuber yield under elevated temperatures in a biparental diploid crossing population [42]. Recently the positive impact of a specific HSc70 allele on tuber yield under heat stress was confirmed in field trials [46]. Gautam et al. performed a GWAS on heat-induced changes in tuber yield and several quality traits on a Texan diversity panel and identified several QTL [43]. So far, no genetic study was conducted on the impact of heat on the aboveground part of the plant, assimilate allocation and tuber starch content.

This study aims to help closing this gap in order to understand the genetic variation underlying heat adaptation. Therefore, we investigated the morpho-physiological effects of moderate heat stress in 178 potato cultivars. A genome-wide association study (GWAS) was conducted in order to identify QTL and markers that underlie heat stress adaptation. We employed eight different genetic architectures (see Section 7.8) to increase the sensitivity of QTL detection and estimated haploblock boundaries to narrow down the QTL regions. Since mainly additive genetic effects are transmittable in breeding programs [47,48], we focused on identifying candidate genes in a haploblock that were identified using the additive gene model. We revealed several QTL for each trait and performed downstream analyses to confine the number and functional composition of underlying genes. Overall, our results may assist in the development of molecular markers to select breeding candidates for the improvement of *S. tuberosum* to the extreme climate conditions that are expected regarding the advancing climate crisis.

The present research intends to answer following research hypotheses: (i) Are there varieties within the investigated panel of tetraploid potato cultivars that are tolerant or sensitive across all investigated traits? (ii) Is the physiological response to heat stress a polygenic trait or controlled by only few major genes? (iii) Is there a distinct and strong population structure? (iv) Which genomic regions are associated with heat-mediated changes in the investigated morpho-physiological traits? (v) Can the collected data be used to estimate heritability and breeding values concerning heat stress adaptation? (vi) Are there known heat-stress associated genes within identified genomic regions during GWAS, and which therefore might be tagged by significant markers?

2. Results

2.1. Phenotypic data analyses

In order to identify heat-tolerance associated genomic regions, phenotypic traits which are strongly affected by elevated temperatures, such as tuber starch content, tuber yield, shoot elongation, green fresh weight, and harvest index (HI), were determined (Fig. 1A-E). To this end, 178 distinct potato cultivars were grown for 5 weeks in control conditions (21/19 °C) until tuberization started. In addition, we monitored flowering stage at this time point (Suppl. Table 1). After that, half of the plants were subjected to a two-week period of moderately elevated temperatures (29 °C/27 °C, referred to as heat) while the other plants remained in control conditions. (See Suppl. Table 1)

Overall, two weeks of heat resulted in enhanced shoot elongation, a weak increase in green fresh weight, and a reduction in tuber yield, HI as well as in tuber starch content in most genotypes (Fig. 1A-E). The data distribution for each trait covered a wide spectrum. For further analysis, differences between heat and control were calculated for each trait and genotype. Differences in tuber starch content (Starch_diff) ranged between –562 and 414 µmol/g.

Shoot elongation during two weeks of stress (Elongation_diff) varied between –9 and 17 cm between heat and control treated plants. Differences in yield (Yield_diff) varied between –56 and 33 g and green fresh weight (GFW_diff) ranged between –27 and 26 g. Both latter traits were used for calculating HI differences (HI_diff), which fluctuated between –0.5 and 0.15 in this panel. Neither of our investigated traits correlated with the flowering stage at the beginning of heat stress (Suppl. Fig. 1 and Suppl. Table 1).

Two varieties, which differ greatly in their morphological heat responses, are presented as examples (Fig. 1G+H). Cultivar Sieglinde exhibited a stronger hyponasty, earlier leaf senescence and heat-induced shoot elongation with an Elongation_diff value of 12.5 cm, in contrast to Zarina, which only reacted with slight visual changes and elongated alike under heat and control conditions (Elongation_diff = 0 cm). Varieties with strong heat-mediated shoot elongation and reduction in traits like Yield_diff, HI_diff and Starch_diff were considered the most sensitive ones within this study (e.g., Sieglinde, Fig. 1H). In contrast, other cultivars that responded only with little changes in these traits were regarded as more tolerant varieties (e.g., Zarina, Fig. 1G). For each trait (Elongation_diff, Yield_diff, HI_diff and Starch_diff) the heat-induced differences were ranked and the 25 % most and least responsive varieties were determined. Across all varieties, five were classified as particularly sensitive and six showed a higher tolerance regarding heat mediated changes in these traits. However, not all varieties responded to the same degree concerning the different traits. For a complete overview of the phenotypic data for all cultivars see Suppl. Table 1

Next, we examined associations between the investigated traits by correlating the heat to control differences to each other using Tau's correlation coefficient [49] (Fig. 1F). Elongation_diff correlated positively with GFW_diff ($\tau = 0.17$), whereas Yield_diff and HI_diff exhibited a negative correlation with Elongation_diff ($\tau = -0.26$ and $\tau = -0.30$). Furthermore, there was a positive correlation between Starch_diff and

Fig. 1. Summary of all traits tested during GWAS. (A-E) Density plots of each trait, separated by control conditions (blue) and heat stressed plants (red). Vertical lines as well as text within plots indicate mean values for the respective trait and condition. (F) Correlation matrix of all phenotypic trait data (heat to control difference) used in the GWAS. Lower triangle: Scatter plots of all pairs of traits. Red trend lines were calculated using the LOESS method. Grey regions indicate 95 % confidence intervals. Upper triangle: Kendall's τ correlation coefficient, significance thresholds p-value below: * 0.05, ** 0.01, *** 0.001. (G-H) Two plants of the more tolerant cultivar Zarina (G) and two plants of the more sensitive cultivar Sieglinde (H) after two weeks under control and heat conditions.

Yield_diff ($\tau = 0.21$). As the HI includes both yield and green fresh weight, HI_diff showed a positive or negative correlation with Yield_diff ($\tau = 0.60$) or GFW_diff ($\tau = -0.37$), respectively.

2.2. Sequencing data analyses

In parallel to the phenotyped 178 cultivars, additional 84 varieties were sequenced, resulting in a total of 261 sequenced cultivars. The sequencing data was obtained using genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) [50]. The utilized restriction enzymes (REs) for GBS were *ApeK1* and *Pst1*, which were shown before to be methylation-sensitive [51,52],

leading to an enrichment of sequencing fragments in euchromatic gene-rich regions. Fig. 2 highlights the usefulness of the approach for identifying regions harbouring candidate genes using GWAS. There, the density of the sequenced reads (C) correlated strongly with the gene density according to the genome annotation (B). The density of reads is also mirrored by the frequency of single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) (D), which abound in gene-rich regions.

In total, 1.27B reads were generated with an average of 4.4 M reads per sample. After adapter and quality trimming, 1.19B reads in total and on average 4.13 M reads per sample (93.7 %) were kept for subsequent analyses. After alignment, 95.5 % of all reads were mapped and properly

Fig. 2. Circular plot of genomic data distribution. (A) Karyogram of the 12 canonical chromosomes of *S. tuberosum*. The centromeres are indicated by red bars. (B) Gene density according to the gff3 annotation file of the DM 1–3516 R44 potato.v6.1 reference genome [112]. (C) Density of reads throughout the genome over all sequenced cultivars. 0.1 % of all reads were randomly sampled for density calculation. (D) Genomic positions of the 20,695 SNPs used for the Starch diff GWAS.

paired, with no secondary alignments and 1.8 % of chimeric alignments. Initial variant calling detected about 3.6 M variants, of which approximately 3 M (85 %) were classified as SNPs. Applying a series of strict filters (see Section 7.4), yielded approx. 38 k high-quality SNPs for population structure and linkage disequilibrium analyses. Because a linear regression of phenotypic values vs. genotypic information is applied on each SNP during GWAS, only marker data for phenotyped individuals can be used. Additionally, imbalance of observations per dosage class needs to be regularized. This was done by allowing no dosage class to contain more than 95 % of the observations for any trait (see Section 7.4). This resulted in around 20 k SNPs for the GWAS of each trait. Taking Starch_diff as a proxy for all traits, the average minor allele frequency (MAF) for the markers used during GWAS was 0.2 and the average polymorphic information content (PIC) was 0.24. This constitutes a strong improvement in quality compared to the set of all 38 k SNPs, which showed an average MAF of 0.07, an average PIC of 0.09, and strongly right-skewed distributions for both metrics (Suppl. Fig. 2). These attributes indicate a low usability of many otherwise high-quality SNPs for GWAS and highlights the importance of analysis-specific filtering of genomic data.

2.3. Genomic analyses

2.3.1. Population structure and genomic differentiation

The relatedness between cultivars was estimated using a genetic distance metric according to Nei [53,54]. With a mean \pm sd distance of 0.3 ± 0.07 , the investigated population does show substantial differentiation between individuals. A histogram of the distances (Suppl. Fig. 3) shows a bimodal distribution of distances. The smaller distribution of

large distances between 0.6 and 0.8 stems from the pairwise distances between any tetraploid cultivar in the panel and any of the three cultivars Inca Sun, Mayan Gold and Mayan Twilight, all of which are diploid and belong to the Group Phureja. All pairwise distances are shown in Fig. 3. Population structure was calculated using the Ward.D2 algorithm. Since it has been shown before that population structure in cultivated potato is rather weak, bootstrapping was conducted to evaluate the stability of the clusters (see Section 7.5 and Fig. 3). The first branching has a bootstrapping value of 100 and differentiates the three diploid Phureja cultivars (subpopulation 3, red) from all the other cultivars in the panel, indicating the usefulness of the approach for population structure estimation in the studies population. After that, a bootstrap value of 97.6 differentiates 109 cultivars of mostly German origin (subpopulation 2, green) and the remaining 149 cultivars (subpopulation 1, blue) of mostly Dutch origin. Nevertheless, the distinguishing between German and Dutch cultivars is not clear-cut with many cultivars of Dutch origin being in subpopulation 2 and several German varieties that can be found within subpopulation 1.

Interestingly, all remaining bootstrap value attain large values close to the leaves of the tree, while becoming very small or not determinable with increasing merging of branches. These results indicate strong kinship but weak overall population structure.

The magnitude of differentiation between the identified subpopulations was determined using the ρ statistic which was developed by Ronfort et al. [55]. It was shown that this parameter is independent of ploidy level and rate of double reduction [56]. The analysis yielded values of $\rho_{12} = 0.04$, $\rho_{13} = 0.44$ and $\rho_{23} = 0.46$. The Phureja cultivars show strong genetic difference from all other cultivars, however, there is only weak differentiation between subpopulations 1 and 2. Both results

Fig. 3. Genetic relationship of the potato panel. Left: dendrogram based on Ward.D2 hierarchical clustering using pairwise distances between cultivars. Right: Heatmap of the genetic dissimilarity matrix calculated using Nei's pairwise distance between all cultivars. The diagonal values in blue indicate a genetic distance of 0. Genetic distances ranged from 0.004 to 0.79 with an average genetic distance across the panel of 0.3. The number of plausible clusters was determined using 1000 bootstrapping iterations. The bootstrapping values are shown as node labels. The color legend refers to values in the heatmap.

can be verified upon checking Fig. 3. Analysis of molecular variance (AMOVA) on the 3 subpopulations revealed that only about 2.1 % of the genetic variance in the whole population is attributable to the formation of subpopulations, 4.3 % of the variance occurs between samples within subpopulations and 93.6 % of the genetic variance is attributable to the within-sample allelic variation.

2.3.2. Nucleotide diversity and evolutionary neutrality

While the previous population structure analyses revealed strong differentiation between the Phureja cultivars and the remaining varieties, it does not show the genomic regions responsible for these differences and no potentially differing genomic regions between subpopulations 1 and 2. To this end, nucleotide diversity π was calculated for each genomic position and subpopulation individually. The results are shown in Suppl. Fig. 4. Nucleotide diversity is significantly lower in subpopulation 3 (red) compared to subpopulations 1 and 2 (blue and green, respectively), which in turn show almost identical genomic profiles. There are a few regions where the nucleotide diversity of subpopulation 3 is higher than in the other two subpopulation, e.g., at around 70 Mb on chr01, 5 Mb on chr03 and 4.2 Mb on chr08. However, since the subpopulations differ greatly in size, the nucleotide diversity alone is not sufficient to compare them. Tajima's D [57] was calculated for each chromosome to investigate whether the observation nucleotide diversity is higher or lower than expected. Averaged over all chromosomes, the D values for each subpopulation were $D_1 = -0.54$, $D_2 = -0.28$ and $D_3 = 0.96$. These results show that the subpopulations 1 and 2 have lower genetic diversity than expected while subpopulation 3 exhibits a larger nucleotide diversity than expected under neutral conditions.

2.3.3. Linkage disequilibrium and LD-decay

Chromosome-wise linkage disequilibrium (LD) and LD-decay were calculated to obtain a first estimate of boundaries around significant loci during GWAS (see Section 7.7). The estimated parameters are reported in the first 5 columns in Table 1. On average, LD decayed by 0.2 in the within 0.5 Mb, by half at 1.45 Mb and to the standard background level

Table 1

LD and LD-decay estimates from this study and from Sharma et al. [40].

Chr.	$r_{max,90\%}^2$	LD _{4/}	LD _{1/}	LD _{1/}	$r_{max,90\%}^2$	LD _{1/}	LD _{1/}
		5max, 90%	2max, 90%	10max, 90%		90, S	2max,90%, S
1	0.40	0.63	1.85	3.37	0.27	1.10	1.61
2	0.45	0.48	1.40	2.81	0.29	1.08	1.74
3	0.51	0.50	1.47	3.25	0.26	1.35	1.93
4	0.35	0.58	1.70	2.89	0.27	1.02	1.52
5	0.35	0.45	1.32	2.26	0.21	1.42	1.50
6	0.54	0.38	1.11	2.44	0.33	0.97	1.72
7	0.39	0.57	1.66	3.01	0.27	1.05	1.59
8	0.46	0.54	1.58	3.20	0.26	1.03	1.48
9	0.41	0.53	1.55	2.89	0.24	0.97	1.24
10	0.79	0.30	0.89	2.40	0.36	0.96	1.92
11	0.50	0.46	1.35	2.88	0.19	1.27	1.13
12	0.33	0.50	1.44	2.32	0.17	1.02	0.80
Average	0.46	0.50	1.44	2.81	0.26	1.10	1.52

$r_{max,90\%}^2$ indicates the maximum LD within the 90th percentile. LD_{4/5max,90%}, LD_{1/2max,90%} and LD_{1/10max,90%} represent the physical distances in Mb at which the LD has decayed to 0.8, 0.5 and 0.1 of its maximum value in the 90th percentile, respectively. The appended subscript S in the three right columns indicates values taken from [40].

of 0.1 at a pairwise distance of 2.8 Mb between markers. LD-decay plots over all chromosomes can be seen in Fig. 4. These results were compared with a recently published study by Sharma et al. [40] who studied the utility of GBS in potato, with respect to LD-decay and GWAS (see Table 1). The $r_{max,90\%}^2$ values from the present study are systematically higher than the ones reported by them as well as the LD_{1/2max,90%} values. The LD_{1/2max,90%} values in this study are almost twice as large as found in [40] (Table 1). The reasons for differences between these numbers are discussed below.

Fig. 4. Chromosome-level LD-decay. Linkage disequilibrium (LD) in form of Pearson's r^2 for each pair of SNPs was calculated and plotted against the physical distance between the SNPs on the chromosome. The red line is a quantile regression of the 90th quantile of r^2 with 5 degrees of freedom. The blue line indicates the standard background LD-decay ($r^2 = 0.1$).

2.3.4. Discriminant analysis of principal components

It has been shown before that discriminant analysis of principal components (DAPC) is superior to other population structure methods used in GWAS for controlling p -value inflation in potato [58]. To obtain the optimal number of clusters for sub-population assignment, 10 iterations of the k -means clustering for up to 15 clusters were performed. This resulted in a minimum average Bayesian information criterion (BIC) when using 4 clusters (Suppl. Fig. 5), which was used as number of genetic clusters in the subsequent DAPC. Cross-validation (CV) was employed to assess the optimal number of principal components (PCs) for DAPC, yielding 114 PCs which cumulatively explained 77.5 % of the genetic variance. All three discriminant functions were retained for cluster assignment. Most cultivars were assigned to the same cluster (cluster 2, 222 cultivars), while the remaining 39 cultivars were clustered within the 3 other clusters. Cluster 3 consisted of the three diploid Phureja cultivars included in this panel and five additional cultivars. Finally, cluster 1 consisted of many cultivars originating from breeders in the southern region of Germany. For a complete list of the subpopulation memberships of all cultivars, see Suppl. Table 2 and Suppl. Fig. 6. The subpopulation assignments were used as part of the subsequent GWAS.

2.4. Association analysis

2.4.1. Significant marker analysis

The GWAS was conducted on the 5 aforementioned traits, which are influenced by heat stress [6,8,10,22,27]. Cultivars with incomplete information regarding a specific trait were excluded prior to GWAS analysis. This resulted in variations in both the numbers and compositions of genotypes analyzed in each individual GWAS (Table 2). To improve the signal detection rate, all 8 possible genetic models for tetraploid genomes were employed [58]. Considering all traits and models simultaneously, significant markers were identified on all 12 chromosomes (see Suppl. Figs. 7–11 for the Manhattan plots of all traits and models and Suppl. Table 3 for summary statistics of all significant markers). Overall, 132 markers attained significant scores, of which 117 markers were unique. 14 markers were significant for both Yield_diff and HI_diff and one marker was significant for HI_diff and GFW_diff (Suppl. Fig. 12F). The number of identified markers per trait ranges from 4 to 39 (Table 2). For all traits, significant markers were called by more than one genetic model, showing a certain degree of redundancy between the employed models (Suppl. Fig. 12A-E). Any individual marker explained up to 13 % of the phenotypic variance, with a trait-dependent average R^2 between 6 % for HI_diff and 9 % for GFW_diff.

Omission of population structure (K model) did not change the results of the GWAS compared to the inclusion of population structure (Q

Table 2

Summary information of the GWAS for the different traits. QTL: quantitative trait locus/loci, M_{eff} : Number of effectively independent genomic regions based on calculations adapted from [61], sig. Thresh: Significance threshold according to [61], λ : Genomic inflation factor with (Q + K) and without (K) population structure considered as fixed covariate during GWAS.

Trait	Samples	Makers	Sig. markers	QTL	Haplo-blocks	M_{eff}	sig. Thresh	λ_{Q+K}	λ_K
Starch_diff	148	20,695	34	13	13	227	3.66	1.06	1.06
Yield_diff	175	21,761	39	21	16	266	3.73	1.02	1.02
Elongation_diff	178	20,608	17	13	11	264	3.72	1.10	1.10
GFW_diff	178	20,608	4	3	2	264	3.72	0.96	0.96
HI_diff	172	21,761	38	17	13	266	3.73	1.04	1.04

+ K model) regarding the logarithm of odds (LOD) score for each SNP (see Suppl. Fig. 13 and 14) as well as genomic inflation factors (compare λ_{Q+K} and λ_K in Table 2). For the phenotypic distribution for each significant SNP and trait see Suppl. Fig. 15–19.

2.4.2. QTL and haploblock identification

For QTL identification, chromosome-wise $LD_{1/2max,90\%}$ values were used to determine the QTL boundaries around each significant marker. In total, 67 QTL were identified (Table 2), each containing between 1 and 13 significant markers. The smallest detected QTL was the first one

located on chromosome 10 (QTL_10_1) for Elongation_diff, spanning 1.78 Mbp. The largest QTL was QTL_2_2 of the Starch_diff trait, spanning 5.57 Mbp. Summing over all QTL per trait, the total number of genes was between 659 for GFW_diff and 4608 for Yield_diff.

In order to improve the QTL boundary resolution, LD heatmaps of the LD matrices around significant markers were examined and genomic clusters of high LD values were identified (hereafter referred to as haploblocks). For most QTL, a single haploblock could be identified that contained all significant markers of the respective QTL. For 16 of the 67 QTL, no apparent lower or upper haploblock boundaries were

Fig. 5. Genomic localization of all identified haploblocks for all investigated traits. The haploblocks are color-coded according to the respective trait: yellow = Starch_diff; red = Yield_diff; blue = Elongation_diff; green = GFW_diff; brown = HI_diff. Centromeric regions are highlighted in red on the karyoplast.

observable. In these cases, the $LD_{1/2max,90\%}$ boundaries were employed as haploblock boundaries.

For four QTL (Starch_diff_2_2, Yield_diff_11_4, HI_diff_1_7 and HI_diff_5_1), multiple potential haploblocks per QTL could be identified that separated the significant markers into different local haplotypes. For example, the 5 significant markers within QTL_1_7 of the trait HI_diff were located in two distinct haploblocks containing 4 markers and 1 marker, respectively (see Suppl. Fig. 20). For the majority of QTL, the identified haploblocks containing the significant markers were smaller than the QTL themselves, with an average decrease in size of 14.4%. As a consequence, the number of genes within the majority of haploblocks decreased as compared to the corresponding QTL. The largest reduction occurred for Elongation_diff, where a total of 2,467 genes remained in the haploblocks as opposed to the 3,250 genes within the QTL. Suppl. Table 4 contains lists of all genes that are located in each haploblock.

Visualization of the haploblock distribution for the various traits throughout the genome showed an overlap between several of them, e.g., on the Chr 01, 03, 04, 07, 09, and 10 (Fig. 5). Most often, the haploblocks of HI_diff coincide with those from Yield_diff (Chr 01, 09 and 10). This can largely be explained by the 14 significant SNPs for both, Yield_diff and HI_diff (Suppl. Fig. 8F). These SNPs tag causal loci that influence yield reduction under heat stress without having an effect on the GFW of the plant. The overlap of GFW_diff haploblock 4_1_1 and HI_diff haploblock 4_1_1 represents a locus influencing GFW in a sufficient degree to also be significant for the harvest index, but without having influence on the yield change under heat. The effect of the SNPs causing the overlapping haploblocks of Starch_diff and Yield_diff on 42 Mbp of Chr 11 shows that cultivars carrying 3 copies of the alternative allele at these positions show a much lower reduction in yield and starch content under heat stress than cultivars carrying up to 3 alternative alleles. For the overlapping haploblocks of Elongation_diff and HI_diff at 54 Mbp of Chr 07, the markers underlying those haploblocks had different effects on the respective traits, indicating different causal loci within the same haploblock acting on these traits. The only clear three-trait overlap of haploblocks occurred at 54 Mbp of Chr 09. The underlying SNPs show only small pairwise LD, indicating absence of pleiotropy for any causal locus in the identified haploblock. However, colocalization of different causal SNPs in the same haploblocks can still result in genetically correlated traits.

2.4.3. GO-term enrichment analysis of identified haploblocks

Since heat stress tolerance is considered a complex trait and therefore controlled by multiple loci, a significant SNP during the GWAS could be tagging multiple genes within the QTL. In order to investigate whether the significant SNPs tag a particularly large number of genes belonging to certain physiological pathways, a gene ontology (GO) enrichment analysis was performed on genes which are located in identified haploblocks for each trait (Suppl. Table 5 and Suppl. Fig. 21). The GO enrichment for the Starch_diff GWAS genes revealed several calmodulin coding genes (calcium-mediated signaling), ASMT and COMT1 coding for genes involved in melatonin biosynthesis and genes coding for sucrose transporters such as SWEETs or SUT1. The GO enrichment for Yield_diff showed an overrepresentation of genes involved in cytokinin biosynthesis and nitrate assimilation and response. Among them was a gene coding for a homologue of the nitrate transporter NRT1.5 and several genes coding for Nodule-inception-like proteins, which modulate nitrate sensing and metabolism [59,60].

2.4.4. Haploblock 12_1_1 of Starch_diff

With 13 significant markers, the QTL Starch_diff 12_1 of the trait Starch_diff contained more significant markers than any other QTL in this study. Six of these markers exceeded the significance threshold assuming additive marker dosage effects, while the remaining seven markers attained scores only marginally below the significance threshold. All 13 significant markers are in strong LD with each other (absolute value of pairwise LD between any pair was ≥ 0.73). The

additive model has a more intuitive biological interpretation than other models. It assumes a fixed amount of change in the phenotypic values with each additional copy of the alternative allele. Since alleles and not genotypes are inherited by the offspring, additive effects are the most important ones for breeding approaches [47,48]. These aspects render this QTL attractive for a more detailed investigation. Fig. 6A shows the Manhattan plot for the Starch_diff trait under the additive genetic model with all QTL shown as markers exceeding the significance threshold proposed by Li and Ji [61] (red line). No markers exceeded the Bonferroni threshold (blue line) for that model. Fig. 6B shows boxplots of the dosage-dependent difference in the starch content between heat stress and control conditions for the two markers within the QTL that attained the highest scores. While the marker *chr12_1013434* shows an increased reduction of starch content under heat stress with additional copies of the alternative allele, the opposite is true for the marker *chr12_1056708*. Both markers explain 11% and 12% of the phenotypic variance at that QTL, respectively. The two markers have a pairwise correlation coefficient of -0.75 , thereby likely tagging the same causal marker, but in a reciprocal fashion. Fig. 6C displays the combined LocusZoom and Hapview-like plot for the QTL Starch_diff_12_1. Two haploblocks can be recognized, of which only the upstream one contains significant markers. This haploblock ranged from 0 to 1.41 Mbp, which is a relaxed boundary and accounts for the possibility that unknown SNPs between the two haploblocks might still be in high LD with those in the upstream haploblock. The haploblock contained 167 genes, as opposed to the 347 genes that were within QTL boundaries, constituting a reduction of putative candidate genes for further investigation of 52%.

Out of all significant markers for all traits, 4 were found to be positioned within the coding sequence of 2 genes and are predicted to cause missense mutations. All 4 markers are located in the aforementioned haploblock 12_1_1 (Fig. 6) and were significant for the Starch_diff trait.

The two markers *chr12_361890* and *chr12_361932* are located in the *StCMT3-12 A* gene (Soltu.DM.12G000130), which encodes a member of the cytosine-5 DNA methyltransferases (C5-MTases) protein family [62]. The alternative alleles are predicted to cause the mutations P79S (*chr12_361890*) and V65L (*chr12_361932*). The pairwise LD between both markers is 1, showing a perfect correlation of allele frequencies between both loci in the investigated population. This means that the protein is either present in the wildtype form or as a double mutant in the studied panel.

The second affected protein is StASHH3 (Soltu.DM.12G000190), a histone-lysine N-methyltransferase belonging to the SET domain-containing (SDG) methyltransferases [63,64]. The two significant markers (*chr12_406954* and *chr12_402510*) are potentially leading to the missense mutations I219V and G387R, respectively. Similar to the markers described above, *chr12_406954* and *chr12_402510* show a pairwise LD of 1. Also, the two markers in *StCMT3-12 A* and those in *StASHH3* have pairwise LD values of 0.9, indicating a mutual occurrence of the alternative protein sequences.

To evaluate which physiological pathway was most likely tagged by the significant SNPs in the haploblock, a GO enrichment analysis with the 167 genes of the corresponding haploblock was performed. Several significantly enriched pathways were identified (Suppl. Fig. 22). These include signal transduction, unsaturated fatty acid biosynthesis, hormone signaling, regulation of photomorphogenesis and detection of calcium. This haploblock contains 17 genes encoding for receptor-like proteins involved in signal transduction, as well as 9 genes encoding for fatty acid desaturases, crucial in unsaturated fatty acid biosynthesis (Suppl. Table 6). Furthermore, 8 genes coding for leucine-rich repeat domain-containing kinases, which are involved in hormone signaling were found as well as 3 genes coding for calmodulin proteins present in both functional groups: regulation of photomorphogenesis and calcium ion detection.

2.4.5. Co-localization of identified haploblocks and heat-related genes

Several gene families related to heat stress response in potato have

Fig. 6. Summary of QTL *Starch_diff_12.1*. (A) Manhattan plot of the *Starch_diff* trait investigated using the additive genetic model. Significant markers and those within $LD_{1/2, 90\%}$ of the significant markers distance are highlighted. Using the additive model, significant associations were detected on chromosomes 1, 2, 11 and 12, respectively. The red line represents the L_i and J_i threshold [61], the blue one the Bonferroni threshold for significance. (B) Distribution of difference in starch content between heat and control conditions for each dosage at the two significant marker positions *chr12_1013434* and *chr12_1056708*. The blue horizontal line indicates no difference in starch content between control and heat-stress conditions. More negative values represent stronger reduction of starch content under heat stress. (C) LocusZoom and Haploview plots for QTL *Starch_diff_12.1* as determined using $LD_{1/2, 90\%}$ boundaries. In the Locuszoom plot, warmer colors indicate stronger LD with the lead SNP (purple). In the haploview plot, warmer colors indicate stronger LD between pairs of markers. Two distinct haploblocks are visible and highlighted by black triangles.

been identified recently [65–67]. Therefore, co-localization of those genes with the identified haploblocks was investigated. The focus laid on *heat shock transcription factors (Hsf)* and *HSP* encoding genes since they play an essential role in thermotolerance adaptation in plants by maintaining a functional proteome [42,68,69]. Genes coding for *Hsf*, *HSP20* and *HSP70* family members have recently been investigated in potato [65–67]. Using their annotation, we screened the haploblocks and found a large overlap (Suppl. Fig. 23). We detected 9 *Hsf*, 9 *HSP20* and 7 *HSP70* genes within our identified haploblocks (Suppl. Table 4). In the following we highlight some candidates found in our and previous studies as responsive to heat.

For instance, *Hsf019* was found within *Starch_diff* haploblock 2.2.2. Varieties containing a higher number of the reference allele (C) at

chr02_40659193 or the alternative allele (G) at *chr02_41601355* exhibited less pronounced reductions in starch contents (Suppl. Table 3+4 and Suppl. Fig. 15). *HSP70-17 (Hsc70)* according to Trapero-Mozos et al., [42] colocalizes with *Yield_diff* haploblock 4.1.1. The occurrence of the reference alleles (T) at *chr04_8774562* or (G) at *chr04_8774570* was associated with less yield reduction due to heat (Suppl. Table 3+4 and Suppl. Fig. 16). The largest number of *HSPs* and *Hsfs* was found in haploblocks linked to *Elongation_diff*. For instance, *Hsf001*, *HSP20-7* and *HSP70-19* are present within haploblock 3.1.1, whereas *Hsf004* and *HSP20-25* colocalize with haploblock 8.1.1. A weak heat-induced elongation was associated with an increased copy number of the alternative (T) alleles at *chr08_38431938* and *chr08_38442648*. In contrast, cultivars with multiple copies of the reference allele (T) at

chr08_38796785 showed less pronounced elongation (Suppl. Table 3+4 and Suppl. Fig. 17).

2.5. Genomic estimated breeding values

In addition to the GWAS and subsequent analyses, both narrow-sense and broad-sense heritability were estimated, and genomic best linear unbiased prediction (G-BLUP) was conducted to calculate the genomic estimated breeding values (GEBVs). Heritability estimation yielded narrow-sense heritability between 0.02 for Yield_diff and 0.12 for Elongation_diff. Broad-sense heritability ranged between 0.07 for HI_diff and 0.21 for Elongation_diff. For GFW_diff and Yield_diff, heritability could not be resolved (Table 3 and Suppl. Fig. 24). Due to the low estimated heritability values, GEBVs could only be calculated for the Starch_diff and Elongation_diff traits. To assess accuracy of the estimated breeding values, cross-validation was performed and the correlation between GEBVs and phenotypic values calculated (see Section 7.9 for details). For one fold of the Starch_diff trait, no GEBVs could be calculated due to an estimated narrow-sense heritability of 0. The correlation between GEBVs and phenotypic values was 0 for Starch_diff and 0.16 for Elongation_diff. The small heritability values and the weak to absent correlation between GEBVs and phenotypes indicate a lack of fit of the data for conducting sound genomic prediction. Reasons for that are discussed in Section 3.9.

3. Discussion

3.1. Phenotypic response to heat stress

This study aimed to explore the influence of moderate heat stress on important agronomic traits in up to 178 potato varieties and to identify SNP markers influencing heat adaptability using a GWAS approach. The development of molecular markers that have a positive effect on thermotolerance is becoming increasingly important for breeding of resilient potato plants [26,28,29]. We found that, compared to cultivation under ambient temperature, moderately elevated temperatures induce a thermomorphogenic response in most genotypes, together with a slight increase in green fresh weight and a reduction in yield-derived traits (Fig. 1). This aligns with findings of other studies demonstrating that elevated temperatures induce a shift in assimilate allocation favouring shoot over tuber growth [6,8,10,22,27]. A positive correlation between a declined tuber yield (Yield_diff) and starch content (Starch_diff) indicates that these reductions may arise from an impaired tuber sink strength and tuber filling capacity (Fig. 1F) as also shown in other studies [8,25,27,70].

Although thermomorphogenesis is known as an acclimatization response of plants, the negative correlation between Elongation_diff and Yield_diff or HI_diff indicates that varieties with greater yield losses elongate more strongly. We therefore hypothesize that a severe heat-induced shoot growth is an indicator of heat susceptibility considering the impact on tuber yield. This contradicts findings of Tang et al. since they observed that increased plant growth correlates positively with tuber weight [10]. Their study encompassed 55 commercial potato varieties and the weight of the largest tuber was utilized as yield indicator,

Table 3

Narrow-sense and broad-sense heritability estimations. h^2 : Narrow-sense heritability, H^2 : Broad-sense heritability, SE: Standard error of the estimator, NA: Parameter could not be estimated.

Trait	Samples	$h^2 \pm SE$	$H^2 \pm SE$
Starch_diff	148	0.07±0.03	0.09±0.07
Yield_diff	175	0.02±NA	NA
Elongation_diff	178	0.12±0.03	0.21±0.1
GFW_diff	178	NA	NA
HI_diff	172	0.07±0.02	0.07±0.06

which does not reflect the total tuber weight per plant. Also, the experimental conditions of their study differed from our approach. In our study, we used mother tubers instead of in-vitro culture plantlets, and moderate heat stress (29 °C /27 °C, day/night) was applied for two weeks, when tuberization was induced. In contrast, Tang et al. applied an earlier and more severe heat treatment (35 °C /28 °C, day/night), which also lasted longer, e.g., until a plant age of 102 days. It becomes clear from other studies, that heat response depends not only on genotype, but also on the developmental stage, the stress level and duration (for recent summary see [18]).

3.2. GBS for genetic analyses and GWAS in potato

In this study, around 38 k markers were used for population structure analysis and around 20 k markers were used for the GWAS. The selection of REs for GBS drastically influences the volume/quality trade-off for subsequent marker analyses. Bastien et al. [71] have shown that by using only *ApeK1* during GBS in potato a relatively large number of markers was called, but with an insufficient mean depth per genotype for reliable variant calling in tetraploid organisms [72,73]. In contrast, a two-RE approach using *Pst1* and *Msp1* yielded less than half as many variants, but with sufficient mean depth per genotype for high-accuracy variant calling. Here, the employed combination of *ApeK1* and *Pst1* led to a high number of high-quality markers for both population structure analysis and GWAS.

Sharma et al. have recently published a study investigating the effect of GBS using methylation-sensitive REs on LD-decay estimation and GWAS results [40]. They showed that GBS using this kind of REs is capable of QTL detection with less ascertainment bias and more reliable relatedness structure estimation in *S. tuberosum* when compared with Infinium array SNPs. These results highlight the value that GBS approaches with sensible REs selection hold for the identification of novel QTL of complex traits.

3.3. Linkage disequilibrium analysis

In the present study, the $LD_{1/2,90\%}$ as well as $LD_{1/10max,90\%}$ values were larger than the ones discovered by [40] (see Table 1), although they used a comparable set of REs to the ones employed here. There are multiple reasons for these differences. First, they did not filter their variants using a MAF threshold, while our variants were filtered for $MAF > 0.05$ before LD estimation (see Section 7.7 for details). Vos et al. (Fig. 4 therein) have shown that MAF has a great influence on LD and LD-decay estimations [74]. Variants with lower MAF values contribute to a lower observed maximum LD and faster LD-decay. Second, our analysis had a different parameterization of the *spline* function. Instead of using 100 kb windows for short-range LD estimation, we used *spline* function with two internal nodes, thereby spanning local estimates over several Mb. This also explains the apparent increase in LD with distance for some chromosomes in Fig. 4. This difference in methodology likely contributes to the observed differences in LD-decay estimations. However, since we considered LD-decay values only as initial QTL boundaries and refined those later on using visual LD-pattern around significant SNPs, any potential overestimation of regions around QTL was diminished.

3.4. Population structure of European cultivars

The population used here showed moderate genetic differences at the individual level, while only weak differentiation between sub-populations was detected. Only the three diploid Phureja cultivars are clearly distinguishable from the remaining cultivars. The obvious explanation for this strong differentiation is the genetic makeup of the diploid cultivars studied here, being bred from *Solanum tuberosum* Group *phureja*, which is genetically different from *Solanum tuberosum* Group

tuberosum [41]. Besides that, no strong population differentiation was observable between the remaining two subpopulations. The same observation for panels of tetraploid cultivars has been extensively described within the literature [38,39,58,74–81]. The reasons for this observation are manifold.

First, breeders often do not take a larger genetic population structure into account when selecting potential breeding material, which can result in admixed population and the formation of complex kinship [39,82]. Second, autotetraploid organisms show heterozygosity levels to a degree that can effectively obscure the underlying population structure [39]. Tajima's D values in our analysis lie between -0.54 and -0.28 for subpopulations 1 and 2, respectively, while the statistic attained a value of 0.96 for subpopulation 3. Negative values of this statistic indicate the presence of selective sweeps or population expansion after a recent genetic bottleneck [83]. Both of these phenomena can occur when breeding potato. Selective sweeps occur when mutations around a locus under selection pressure "hitchhike" and are fixed together with the locus under selection. Recently, Jo et al. have identified 86 outlier loci due to attributable selective sweeps during selection for chipping quality in potato [84].

Concerning the bottleneck hypothesis, it is known that new varieties can be as little as six meiotic events away from the ancestral variety from the 19th century [74,85]. Therefore, while being considered a relatively long period for humans, the several hundred years that have passed since the introduction of potato in Europe in the 16th century [86] might not be such a long time regarding genetic recombination of vegetatively propagated crops. This hypothesis also explains partially the large LD-blocks observed here and in other studies and consequently the slow LD-decay estimation [39,40,74].

The $D_3 = 0.96$ of the three diploid cultivars can be explained in parts by balancing selection, where the introgression of Phureja with the other breeding partner created an excess of nucleotide diversity. It has to be kept in mind that the calculation of Tajima's D in this study was done chromosome-wise (see Supp. Table 8). Therefore, short-range variation of the statistic along the genome was not investigated.

3.5. Population stratification during GWAS

In this study, DAPC resulted in the identification of 4 clusters, of which one cluster contained the majority of genotypes. No admixture was detected, indicating a certain degree of overfitting. However, since no difference was detectable regarding p -values between the Q + K-model and the K-model, this indicates that correcting for population structure in potato is not necessarily due to a weak population structure. This conclusion is supported by the existing literature, as mentioned above. Additionally, for some iterations of the k-means algorithm, 3 or 5 subpopulations would have been equally justifiable, showing that there is no clear-cut value for the optimal number of subpopulations in the panel used here, when considering only genetic information. In their seminal GWAS paper in 2006, Yu et al. [87] have listed several levels of structured populations. Our panel resembles both, a type II population (family-based samples) and then a type III (structured population with family-based samples). Yu et al. [87] have also warned that using population structure correction for only weakly structured population may actually result in a loss of statistical power. As we have demonstrated above, population structure does not change the results of our GWAS to a large amount and might therefore be omitted.

3.6. Genome-wide association study

During the GWAS, significant markers were detected on all chromosomes and using all genetic models. Calculation of GWAS significance thresholds according to [61] resulted in around 260 independent regions in the investigated gene-rich parts. Assuming equal haplotype sizes, this indicates sufficient coverage of the genomic regions of interest to detect the majority of QTL in the subsequent GWAS analyses. The

threshold proposed by Li and Ji [61] (red significance threshold in Supplement Fig. 7–11) detected in total 117 unique markers, while only 2 markers attained scores surpassing the Bonferroni threshold (blue significance threshold in Supplement Fig. 7–11). Since yield and starch content are highly quantitative traits [58,88,89], it is reasonable to assume the same holds for the adaptation of plants to heat stress regarding these traits, because heat causes multiple physiological reactions. Therefore, we conclude that the Bonferroni threshold is over-conservative and not appropriate for most GWAS analyses with moderate sample sizes and highly quantitative traits. In contrast, the Li and Ji threshold [61] accounts for the LD between markers and is therefore tailored to the genome architecture of the target panel. Several of the significant markers explained more than 10 % of the phenotypic variance, when evaluated using regression analyses. This indicates that the SNP density was sufficient to catch many medium to large-effect QTL within the genome.

3.7. Influence of over-represented pathways on heat tolerance adaptation

GO-term enrichment analysis was conducted on genes located within the haploblocks for all traits to assess if identified significant SNPs, which might tag a substantial number of genes, were associated with specific physiological pathways (Suppl. Fig. 21 and Suppl. Table 5). Given the increased abundance of genes associated with sucrose transport, like *SUT1* and *SWEETS*, that were found within the identified Starch_diff haploblocks, we hypothesize that variations in heat susceptibility regarding starch losses could arise from differentially impaired sucrose loading, unloading and transport between cultivars similar to previous results [8,25,27,90–92]. The identification of genes associated with nitrate response and assimilation within the Yield_diff haploblocks, along with recent findings highlighting the significant impact of nitrogen availability on tuber formation, suggests a genetic variability in nitrogen utilization [93].

We particularly focused on haplotype 12_1_1 and its effects on the Starch_diff trait. GO-term enrichment analysis of genes located in the corresponding haplotype revealed a high percentage of calmodulin coding genes, as well as genes coding for receptors that are linked to signal transduction and hormone signaling. The activation of calcium and hormone signaling that induce Hsfs and HSPs and increase the antioxidant capacity are well-known heat responses [94–99]. The overrepresentation of genes related to unsaturated fatty acid synthesis in this haplotype (Suppl. Fig. 22 and Suppl. Table 6) suggests that differences in membrane composition influence the capacity of heat adaptation. Unsaturated fatty acid content can increase membrane fluidity and overexpression of fatty acid desaturase encoding genes enhanced tolerance against various stresses [94,100,101]. Hence, the identified desaturase genes might play a role in the regulation of membrane fluidity under heat conditions, thereby indirectly alleviating starch reduction under heat stress.

Overall, our findings align with established stress response mechanisms. Nevertheless, a more detailed analysis of the identified genes and their influence on starch metabolism is required to confirm their role in thermotolerance adaptation in potato.

3.8. Influence of heat-related genes on heat tolerance adaptation

Hsfs and HSPs play an important role in acquiring thermotolerance in various plants [42,68,69,102–104]. Therefore, we analyzed whether members of these gene families are among the haploblocks in our GWAS. *Hsf019* was found to lie within Starch_diff haplotype 2_2_2 and its expression has been shown to be affected by heat in previous studies [65]. We therefore hypothesize that the significant SNPs *chr02_40659193* and *chr02_41601355* which flag this haplotype may contribute to maintain high starch levels during heat stress.

Another study demonstrated that HsfA1d promotes hypocotyl elongation under chilling stress in Arabidopsis [105]. Given the observed

negative correlation between heat-mediated shoot elongation and tuber yield (Fig. 1F), *Hsf* encoding candidates co-localizing with Elongation_diff haploblocks are interesting candidates for further research, such as *Hsf004*. Its expression was found to be drastically increased (300-fold) under short-term heat stress in potato [65]. The corresponding SNP markers (*chr08_38431938*, *chr08_38442648* and *chr08_38796785*) could directly or indirectly affect regulatory elements of *Hsf004* and thereby control shoot elongation during stress.

Moreover, the previously identified candidate gene *HSc70* (= *HSP70-17*) [42] co-localizes with the haploblock 4.1.1 regarding Yield_diff in our study. The previous study used tubers from nodal cuttings kept either under 22 °C or 28 °C for their genetic screen [42]. It also revealed a heat-mediated induction in *HSP70-17* expression in both leaf and tuber already 4 h after elevated temperature treatment. The authors uncovered an allelic variant, which was linked to higher stress tolerance and tuber yield was improved under elevated temperatures in transgenic plants that express this variant. In our study, genotypes harbouring the reference allele T at *chr04_8774562* or G at *chr04_8774570* were associated with weaker yield losses which may suggest a conserved role of this gene. Actually, a recent publication by Campbell et al. [46] presents results from field studies at several location in Africa and UK confirming that *Hsc70* expression correlates with heat stress tolerance in various wild potato relatives and has therefore a high potential for breeding stress-resilient potatoes.

3.9. Heritability and genomic prediction

The genomic estimated heritability of the traits was poor in our study for both narrow-sense as well as broad-sense heritability. Multiple possible explanations exist for this observation. From a biological viewpoint, the response of potato to heat stress as investigated in this study might only have a narrow genetic basis. It is possible that the genetic variation observed in potato in this study does not have a strong influence on the response to heat stress, when considering all available markers simultaneously. This contradicts previous studies which observed a moderate heritability of agronomic traits in heat-stressed potato plants [106,107], achieving estimated heritabilities of over 40 %. However, our experimental setup and methodology differed greatly compared to the above-mentioned studies. Luthra et al. grew a panel of 105 potato cultivars in a single, warm temperature environment in India and estimated a broad-sense heritability of tuber yield (g/plant) of 61 % and of dry matter (%) of 79 % [106]. Although these values are large, the lack of a control environment means that the estimated values only held for the phenotypic variation as obtained in heat-stressed conditions, as opposed to our study, which focused on the investigation of the change in agronomic traits between control and stress conditions.

More comparable to our work is the research conducted by Benavides et al. [107]. They studied the effect of heat stress on potato by using a North Carolina II mating design to create 64 full-sib families which were grown in three field environments with different temperature conditions. They estimated narrow-sense heritability using male and female variance components, resulting in a narrow-sense heritability between 30 % (female component) and 41 % (male component) for tuber yield (g/plant). The differences in their estimates and ours likely reflects what has become known as “missing heritability” [108], which was first observed in human body height [109]. It describes the observation that marker-based heritability estimates are often much lower when compared with family-based regression approaches. The same effect has been observed by Sverrisdóttir et al. [38], who calculated narrow-sense heritability of starch content in potato using a marker-based approach with more than 170,000 SNPs and a parent-offspring regression. Their population consisted 762 offspring and 18 parent lines. They obtained a marker-based heritability estimate of 41 % vs. 90 % when using parent-offspring regression. Although they did not include abiotic stress in their analysis, this result strongly indicates that a lack of informative genomic data leads to a greatly underestimated

heritability.

4. Limitations

The phenotypic differences between heat-treated plants and plants grown under control conditions were used in this GWAS. The differences were used in order to reduce batch effects emerging from separate experiments. This approach ensured that batch effects acting equally strong in both conditions are not propagated to subsequent analyses. However, this approach restricts the use of raw phenotypic data due to lack of their comparability between the different glasshouse experiments. Additionally, further experiments and especially field trials over several years and locations with all investigated cultivars are necessary to evaluate the repeatability of phenotypic measurements. These experiments would show how much of the variation in heat adaptation is attributable to genetic differences between cultivars and how much of it depends on other environmental conditions. However, field trials concerning heat stress come with their own set of limitations and are hard to pile due to adversities regarding controlling temperature over a large open area.

Despite the success in identifying moderate to large-effect QTL, large gaps with no sequence information render the assessment of fine-grain population structure and local linkage between markers difficult. It is expected that by using a high-density marker set, haploblock boundaries may be defined more precisely and more medium to large-effect QTL could be detected. A limiting factor for such an approach is the drastic increase in sequencing costs and computational burden for genomic analyses. The low density of our marker set, especially small-effect and rare SNPs, likely led to a strongly deflated heritability estimate of the traits studied here. This lack in genomic information is propagated to the GEBV calculation, since all available markers are used for the calculation of GEBVs.

However, before interpreting the marker-based estimated heritability values on an absolute scale, it is important to estimate heritability using a family-regression method under similar experimental circumstances for comparison. Additional experiments with a sufficient number of closely related individuals are required to allow estimation of heritability of heat-stress response.

One limiting factor of crop GWAS focusing on abiotic stress response under defined conditions in general is a relatively small sample size owed to the need to accurately control environmental conditions. The sample size of 148 to 178 phenotyped cultivars due to glasshouse capacity led to the observation that for many significant SNPs not all five allele dosages were represented. This problem becomes more severe considering rare markers with low MAF. Therefore, it is likely that many QTL which contain rare variants as well as those which explain only a small amount of phenotypic variance remained undetected in the approach presented here. Since the investigated traits are complex and therefore likely controlled by many QTL, with most of them having only a small effect on the phenotype, an increased sample size will probably reveal many low-effect QTL.

Conducting GWAS under controlled glasshouse conditions limits the number of cultivars that can be investigated but ensures a more stable phenotypic assessment compared to field trials. In addition, it has been shown that moderate sample sizes are sufficient to detect QTL that explain at least 5 % of the phenotypic variance, which is also arguably a lower boundary for biological relevance [110].

5. Perspectives

The insights gained from this study represent a starting point for subsequent research to uncover the mechanisms underlying heat stress-response in potato. In the future, the GWAS can be combined with transcriptome data obtained from selected cultivars grown under control and heat conditions. This approach would allow to validate differential expression of discussed candidates and/or to identify additional

candidate genes within the haploblocks, which were not considered so far. Subsequently, a transgenic approach can be considered, in which expression of candidate genes is altered either by knock down or over-expression strategies. The physiological reactions of those plants under both heat-stress and control conditions will provide direct evidence of their role in heat adaptation.

Alternatively, transcript profiles of all genotypes used for the GWAS would allow to correlate gene expression pattern with allele dosages of significant markers of the GWAS and to identify expression QTL (eQTL), thereby further illuminating the interplay between genomic and transcriptomic components in the light of heat response.

An important next step is the verification of identified markers in a sub-set of genotypes that were genotyped, but not phenotyped yet under heat-stress conditions, before testing verified markers in the field.

6. Conclusion

The morphological and physiological responses of cultivated potato to heat stress are diverse. The investigated cultivars showed a broad spectrum of heat stress adaptation which indicates a rich pool of genetic material for crop improvement. We collected evidence for correlations between phenotypic traits that were previously unknown and may help to illuminate the complex thermotolerance of potato. Additionally, we have shown that population structure interpretation in European cultivars is non-trivial. Here, we could observe strong kinship but weak overall population structure due to the complex genomic architecture and high levels of genetic differences between individual cultivars. By using GBS data and a set of agronomically important traits, such as assimilate allocation and tuber starch content, we were able to detect QTL that serve as valuable initial information for investigating the genomic architecture underlying the broad range of heat-stress responses of cultivated potato varieties. Some of the identified markers have potential to be used in breeding programs to improve the heat tolerance of future potato cultivars. However, comprehensive functional analyses of these regions are required to validate their role and elucidate their mode of action. Additional research is necessary to accurately assess the utility of genomic prediction aiming at heat tolerance in European potato cultivars.

7. Materials and methods

7.1. Plant material and harvest

For phenotypic analysis 178 potato cultivars, predominantly of European origin, were selected based on a similar maturity group (medium-early). We conducted a preliminary experiment in a climate-controlled glasshouse to ensure uniformity of the seed tubers for following phenotyping experiments. Additionally, we harvested leaf samples, which were sent to LGC Genomics GmbH for GBS (see Section 7.3). Tubers produced in this initial experiment were stored in a cool, dark room and served as mother tubers for the subsequent phenotyping experiments.

Due to space limitations in the glasshouse, the 178 cultivars were phenotyped in six consecutive experiments. Within each experiment, 20 to 50 cultivars were analyzed together. For each genotype, four sprouting tubers were planted in 3.5 l pots with mixed substrate (1 % sand, 33 % P-Type and 66 % T-Type Hawita, Vechta, Germany) and grown under control conditions (21/19 °C, day/night) with 16-h light (250–300 $\mu\text{mol quanta m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) and 8-h darkness. After 35 days, around tuber initiation time, two plants per genotype were shifted to a neighboring glasshouse with moderately elevated temperatures (29/27 °C, day/night), while the other two plants remained in the control glasshouse. After 14 days under corresponding conditions plants were harvested and yield-derived traits (shoot elongation, green fresh weight, and yield) were documented for control- and heat-treated plants. HI was determined by dividing tuber yield by total biomass, which is the sum of

yield and green fresh weight. For each trait, the differences (heat minus control) were calculated and are labeled in this study as Elongation_diff, Starch_diff, GFW_diff, Yield_diff and HI_diff. Harvested tubers were stored in a cool, dark room and sampled for starch content measurement after one week.

7.2. Determination of tuber starch contents

Storage parenchyma of all tuber-bearing cultivars were sampled one week after harvest. Four replicates were taken from two tubers of two plants for each genotype and condition. For starch content determination, tuber discs (approx. 50 mg FW) were extracted with 1 ml 80 % (v/v) ethanol and incubated at 80 °C for 60 min. After incubation with 0.2 M KOH overnight, samples were heated for 90 min at 95 °C and neutralized with 1 N acetic acid. Samples were amyloglucosidase digested and glucose contents were determined using a coupled optical assay as described previously [27].

7.3. DNA isolation, sequencing and read pre-processing

In total, DNA samples of 261 distinct cultivars were extracted and sequenced using GBS in two sequencing experiments using Illumina® NovaSeq™ 6000 SP, sequencing 250 bp paired-end reads (see Suppl. Table 7, raw sequencing data can be downloaded from the NCBI SRA database under Project name PRJNA1106415). The first experiment included the 178 phenotyped cultivars and the second contained 84 cultivars, which were not phenotyped so far. DNA isolation and sequencing was conducted by LGC Genomics GmbH. Genome fragmentation for library preparation was achieved by using the endonucleases *ApeK1* and *PstI*. Raw read cleaning prior to alignment was conducted using the BBDuk program from the BBMap package (v38.90) [111]. Reads were adapter-trimmed using a kmer size (*kmer*) of 23 and a minimum kmer size (*mink*) of 11, first from the right end, then from the left end, setting the Hamming distance (*hdist*) to 1. Reference adapter sequences for adapter trimming were provided by the BBMap software. Finally, simultaneous quality trimming from both sides was performed, setting the quality threshold for trimming (*trimq*) to 30 and discarding every read shorter than 35 bp after trimming, to reduce chances of mismatches due to short sequence length.

7.4. Alignment and variant calling

Alignment of reads to the reference genome (DM 1–3516 R44 potato v6.1 [112]) was conducted using bwa-mem (v0.7.17-r1188) [113]. After alignment, BAM files for all samples were coordinate-sorted and indexed using the *sort* and *index* commands from the Samtools software package (v1.12) [114]. Then, all BAM files were concatenated for variant calling using *bamaddrg*. Variant calling was performed using Freebayes (v1.3.2) [115]. Variant filtering and sample filtering for GWAS was performed in the following succession; (i) removing all non-SNP variants, (ii) removing samples with insufficient phenotypic data (this step was only performed for genotypic data used in the GWAS but not for variants used in the population structure analysis), (iii) removing all non-biallelic SNPs, keeping only SNPs with QUAL>30, setting the genotype of any sample to uncalled if the SNP had a read depth of <61 for that sample, (iv) removing any SNP with <90 % call-rate, (v) removing the 5 % of SNPs with maximum read depth to minimize the chance of calling false heterozygotes [116], (vi) keeping only SNPs for which both reference and alternative allele were observed at forward and reverse strand, and (vii) removing all SNPs that turned out monomorphic after preceding filter steps. For the GWAS, after filtering the VCF file for phenotyped samples, the same filters as described above were applied as well as a maximum genotype frequency filter. This guaranteed that no single genotype class (zero to four) harboured more than 95 % of the samples for any given SNP. SNPs violating this filter were discarded before GWAS (see [58] for more information). For LD-

decay estimation, only SNPs with MAF > 0.05 were used.

7.5. Population genetic analyses

Genetic distances between all individuals were calculated using Nei's genetic distance [53,54], as adapted for calculations between individuals within the Poppr package (v.2.9.6) [117,118]. Hierarchical clustering using the Ward.D2 method was applied on the distance matrix to construct a phylogenetic tree. Consistency of the tree was evaluated by a bootstrapping approach using the *aboot* function of the Poppr package and 1000 iterations. Subpopulations were assigned based on the *p*-values of the bootstrapping. Pairwise differentiation of the identified populations was assessed using the *amova* function from the Poppr R package (setting *within* = FALSE, resulting in estimation of ρ as established by [55]). AMOVA was calculated using the same function but considering all subpopulations simultaneously and setting *within* = TRUE. Calculation of nucleotide diversity π was done achieved by the *diversity.stats* function of the R package PopGenome (v2.7.7) [119], setting *pi* = TRUE. Tajima's *D* and other population differentiation parameters reported in Suppl. Table 8 were calculated using the *neutrality.stats* function with *detail* = TRUE and subsequent use of the *get.neutrality* function with *theta* = TRUE, both of which are also part of the PopGenome package.

7.6. Discriminant analysis of principal components

Population stratification for the GWAS was determined using *discriminant analysis of principal components* (DAPC) [120], as implemented in the R package Adegenet (v2.1.5) [121,122] using all 261 cultivars. K-means clustering was performed using *k* = 1 to *k* = 15 clusters and the Bayesian information criterion (BIC) was used for each number of clusters to identify the most plausible number of subpopulations. This process was repeated 10 times to assess the credibility of the identified number of sub-populations. Afterwards, DAPC was conducted using *k* = 4 clusters, as this number of sub-populations produced the smallest BIC on average. Two-fold cross-validation resulted in an optimal number of 114 principal components (PCs) for DAPC, as this number minimized the mean squared error (MSE). The posterior population assignment of each cultivar was then used in the GWAS as a fixed effect to correct for population stratification (Q).

7.7. Linkage disequilibrium

Linkage disequilibrium (LD) was calculated twice. Once for LD-decay estimation by using the MAF-filtered variant calls and once for all SNPs used in the GWAS for all traits to assess potential haploblock structure of QTL. The *multidog* function of the R package Updog (v2.1.2) [72] was used for genotype likelihood estimation. The default prior was chosen [123]. Subsequently, these likelihoods were used to estimate r^2 values using the *mldest* function (for LD-decay) or the *ldfast* function (for haploblock assessment) from the Ldsep package (v2.1.2) [124]. The *bs* function of the Splines package (v4.4.0) and the *rq* function of the Quantreg package (v5.95) with 5 degrees of freedom were used for spline calculation separately for each chromosome (resulting in *K* = 2 internal knots, see [125] for a mathematical explanation). The window sizes ranged from 3.8 Mbp, containing 169 SNPs (chromosome 10) to 59 Mbp, containing 550 SNPs (chromosome 1). This resulted in chromosome-wise $LD_{1/2,90\%}$ values.

7.8. Genome-wide association study

The GWAS was performed using the GWASpoly software (v2.10) [58], as it was developed for the application in autopolyploid organisms such as potato and allows for investigation of all possible gene action models in autotetraploids without the necessity to recode the allele

dosage matrix. This correct handling of allele dosages exceeding two copies of an allele is a feature still missing in many widely used platforms like PLINK [126,127] and GAPIT [128]. For marker effect estimation, the linear mixed model for marker effect assessment as described by Yu et al. [87] was employed:

$$\vec{y} = Q\vec{v} + S_k\vec{\tau}_k + \vec{u} + \vec{e}$$

Here, *y* is the *n* × 1 vector of phenotypic values. *Q* is an *n* × *p* incidence matrix mapping the *n* observations to the *p* subpopulation. *v* is the corresponding vector of subpopulation effects. *S_k* is a *n* × *d* incidence matrix, mapping observations to genotype classes of marker *k*. τ_k is the *d* × 1 marker effect vector of marker *k*. The dimension *d* depends on the gene action models employed during GWAS. In this study, all eight possible gene action models were employed (additive, diploid-additive, general, diploid-general, simplex-dominant and duplex-dominant for the reference and the alternative allele, respectively). The *n* × 1 vector *u* controls for the polygenic background and is modelled as $u \sim N(0, K\sigma_g^2)$, *K* being the genomic estimated kinship matrix. $K = MM^T$ was implemented as genetic covariance matrix for polygenic variance estimate on, where *M* is the *n* × *p* matrix of marker dosages with *n* ranging from 148 to 178 samples and *p* ranging from 20,695 to 21,761 SNPs, depending on the trait under investigation. The columns of *M* were centered before kinship calculation. The *K* matrix was scaled such that the mean of the diagonal elements is 1. To reduce the effect of "proximal contamination" which can occur when a SNP is tested as a fixed effect and a random effect simultaneously [129], the leave-one-chromosome-out (LOCO) method as implemented in the GWASpoly package was used.

A significance threshold for GWAS results was established according to the method proposed by Li and Ji [61], as well as by the Bonferroni-method.

QTL were determined as regions around the positions of significant SNPs $\pm LD_{1/2,90\%}$. Significant SNPs lying within $LD_{1/2,90\%}$ -range of each other were considered belonging to the same QTL, regardless of the gene model for which the SNPs attained a significant score. For any QTL, if there were multiple SNPs with equal maximum score compared to the other significant SNPs within the QTL, the leftmost SNP of those with maximum score was considered the peak position. Partial R^2 were calculated according to the model that reported the peak position. If a QTL had its peak position reported by the additive genetic model, R^2 was the phenotypic variance explained by performing a simple linear regression of the phenotypic values against all 5 alternative allele dosages, coded as (0,1,2,3,4). If the peak position of a QTL was reported by the general model, an ANOVA was conducted to calculate R^2 as residual sum of squares divided by the total sum of squares. This procedure was analogous for all gene models. For further information about the gene models, see [58]. For further QTL investigation, interactive LocusZoom-like plots and LD-heatmaps were created for each preliminary QTL using Plotly [130]. Where clear LD boundaries could be determined using the heatmap of all pair-wise LD-values around a QTL, that QTL range was further refined and called haploblock. If no refinement was possible, the $LD_{1/2,90\%}$ distance around the outermost significant SNPs in any QTL was kept as haploblock boundary. The number of genes lying in each QTL and haploblock was reported.

7.9. Genomic prediction

Heritability estimation and genomic prediction were performed using the Sommer R package (v4.3.5.) [131]. The additive and dominance relationship matrices *A* and *D* were constructed using the *A.mat* and *D.mat* functions, respectively. Narrow-sense and broad-sense heritability were estimated using the *mmer* function, with the *A* and *D* matrices as variance-covariance matrices according to the following formulae:

$$\vec{y} = \vec{\mu} + \vec{a} + \vec{d} + \vec{e}$$

$$\text{var}(\vec{y}) = \text{var}(\vec{a}) + \text{var}(\vec{d}) + \text{var}(\vec{e}) = A\hat{\sigma}_A^2 + D\hat{\sigma}_D^2 + I\hat{\sigma}_E^2$$

$$\hat{h}^2 = \hat{\sigma}_A^2 / (\hat{\sigma}_A^2 + \hat{\sigma}_D^2 + \hat{\sigma}_E^2)$$

$$\hat{H}^2 = (\hat{\sigma}_A^2 + \hat{\sigma}_D^2) / (\hat{\sigma}_A^2 + \hat{\sigma}_D^2 + \hat{\sigma}_E^2)$$

Here, \vec{a} , \vec{d} and \vec{e} are the additive, dominant and residual effects, \hat{h}^2 and \hat{H}^2 are the estimated narrow-sense and broad-sense heritabilities, respectively.

GEBVs were assessed using a similar model but omitting the dominant term \vec{d} from the above equation and solving for the breeding values \hat{a} under the assumption that $\vec{a} \sim N(0, A\sigma_A^2)$. To assess the accuracy of GEBVs for the feasible traits (Starch_diff and Elongation_diff), 10-fold cross-validation was performed. For each fold, 10 % of the phenotypic data were masked before breeding value estimation (10 observation for Starch_diff, 18 observations for Elongation_diff) and the model trained with the remaining 90%. Then, the GEBVs were correlated with the phenotypic values of the test cultivars for each fold.

7.10. Go-term enrichment analysis

A GO-term enrichment analysis was performed on the best hit to the Arabidopsis proteome, which was based on the recently published and improved assembly (v6.1) of DM 1–3516 R44 potato.v6.1 [112]. Based on the published high confidence representative gene models, only primary transcripts were included in this analysis. GO term to pathway name annotations were downloaded from TAIR. Enrichment analysis was performed using the Bioconductor package clusterProfiler (v4.10.0) and R software (v4.3.2) [132,133]. Investigated pathways had a minimum and maximum number of genes of 10 and 1000. Enrichments with Bonferroni ≤ 0.05 were accepted as significant.

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Consent for publication

All authors agree to publish.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Alexander Kaier: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Selina Beck:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Markus Ingold:** Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **José María Corral:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Stephan Reinert:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Uwe Sonnewald:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sophia Sonnewald:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ygeno.2024.110954>.

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